

Infrared spectra of *N*-aryl substituted amides 2/4- $\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHCOR}$ ($\text{R} = \text{H}, \text{CH}_3, \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3, \text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2, \text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ or $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Cl}$; $\text{X} = \text{H}, \text{Cl}$ or CH_3 and $i = 0, 1, 2$ or 3)

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Several *N*-(aryl)-substituted amides of the general formula, 2/4- $\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHCOR}$ (where $\text{X} = \text{H}, \text{Cl}$ or CH_3 and $\text{R} = \text{H}, \text{CH}_3, \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3, \text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2, \text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ or $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Cl}$) are prepared, characterised and their infrared spectra measured in the solid state and analysed. Generally chloro substitution in the side chain increases the C=O absorptions, while that of methyl groups lower the wave numbers. Amides with trimethyl substituted side chains absorb at higher wavenumbers. But the N-H and C-N stretching vibrations do not show particular trends on side chain substitution. This may be due to the fact that the spectra were recorded in the solid state and the compounds may crystallise in different forms in the solid state. The intercorrelations of C=O and N-H absorption frequencies of all the amides have been made. The correlations are reasonably linear with some exceptions for the reasons stated above.

Amides are one of the classes of organic compounds in which the hydroxy groups of carboxylic acids are replaced by the amino groups. They are represented by the general structure, $\text{R}^1\text{-CO-NX-R}^2$, where $\text{X} = \text{H}, \text{OH}, \text{NR}_2^3, \text{COR}^3, \text{R}^3$ and $\text{R}^1, \text{R}^2, \text{R}^3 = \text{H}, \text{alkyl}$ or aryl group¹. The amides are of fundamental chemical interest as conjugation between nitrogen lone pair electrons and the carbonyl π -bond results in distinctive physical and chemical properties.

We have recently reported the infrared and Raman spectra² and crystal structures³ of several substituted *N*-(phenyl)-2-chloroacetamides, *N*-(phenyl)-2,2-dichloroacetamides and *N*-(phenyl)-2,2,2-trichloroacetamides of the general formulae, $\text{X}_y\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-yNHCOCCH}_2\text{Cl}$, $\text{X}_y\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-yNHCOCCHCl}_2$ and $\text{X}_y\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-yNHCOCCL}_3$, respectively, where $\text{X} = \text{H}, o/m/p\text{-CH}_3, \text{Cl}$ or NO_2 and $y = 1, 2$ or 3 . We report herein the infrared spectra of a number of *N*-(aryl)-substituted amides of the formula, 2/4- $\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHCOR}$ (where $\text{X} = \text{H}, \text{Cl}$ or CH_3 and $\text{R} = \text{H}, \text{CH}_3, \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3, \text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2, \text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ or $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Cl}$). The *N*-(aryl)-substituted amides prepared were *N*-(phenyl)-2-methylacetamide, *N*-(phenyl)-2,2-dimethylacetamide, *N*-(phenyl)-2,2,2-trimethylacetamide, *N*-(phenyl)-2-chlorobenzamide, *N*-(2-chlorophenyl)-2-methylacetamide, *N*-(2-chlorophenyl)-2,2-dimethylacetamide, *N*-(2-chlorophenyl)-2,2,2-trimethylacetamide, *N*-(2-chlorophenyl)-benzamide, *N*-(2-chlorophenyl)-2-chlorobenzamide, *N*-(2-methylphenyl)-acetamide, *N*-(2-

methylphenyl)-2-methylacetamide, *N*-(2-methylphenyl)-2,2-dimethylacetamide, *N*-(2-methylphenyl)-2,2,2-trimethylacetamide, *N*-(4-chlorophenyl)-acetamide, *N*-(4-chlorophenyl)-2-methylacetamide, *N*-(4-chlorophenyl)-2,2-dimethylacetamide, *N*-(4-chlorophenyl)-2,2,2-trimethylacetamide, *N*-(4-methylphenyl)-acetamide, *N*-(4-methylphenyl)-2-methylacetamide, *N*-(4-methylphenyl)-2,2-dimethylacetamide and *N*-(4-methylphenyl)-2,2,2-trimethylacetamide.

Results and discussion

The infrared absorption frequencies of *N*-(phenyl)- and substituted *N*-(phenyl)-amides of the general formula, 2/4- $\text{XC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHCOR}$ (where $\text{X} = \text{H}, \text{Cl}$ or CH_3 and $\text{R} = \text{H}, \text{CH}_3, \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3, \text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2, \text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ or $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Cl}$) are given in Tables 1–5. The frequencies of other substituted amides were also measured and included for comparisons.

The general assignment of different bands in various compounds has been dealt in detail elsewhere⁴. The range of group absorptions has been assigned based on many compounds in which the groups occur. Although the ranges are quite well defined, the precise frequency or wavelength at which a specific group absorbs is dependent on its environment within the molecule and on its physical state.

The C=O stretching vibrations appear as very strong absorptions in the ranges, 1695–1642, 1710–1653, 1705–1637, 1681–1601 and 1732–1600 cm^{-1} for the *N*-

Note

Table 1. Infrared absorption frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCOR}$, where R =

Assignment	CH_3^a	CH_2CH_3	$\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$	$\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$	CH_2Cl^a	CHCl_2^a	CCl_3^a	C_6H_5^a	2- ClC_6H_4
N-H (str)	3305.0 s	3258.1 s	3299.6 s	3312.1 s	3266.8 s	3269.7 s	3290.0 s	3337.0 s	3239.8 s
C-H	-	3198.4 m	3136.7 w	3132.8 w	3099.1 s	3086.5 s	-	-	3189.7 s
(Ar sym str)	-	3086.5 m	-	3050.8 w	3052.8 w	3013.2 s	-	-	3080.7 s
C-H (alk str)	-	2975.6 m	2968.9 m	2966.0 s	-	2948.6 w	-	-	-
	-	2935.1 m	2931.3 w	2932.2 m	2947.7 m	2904.2 w	-	-	-
Combination bands	1760.0 w	-	-	1950.6 w	1938.1 w	1945.8 w	-	-	1968.0 w
C=O (str)	1685.0 s	1666.2 s	1661.4 s	1654.6 s	1673.0 s	1672.0 s	1695.0 s	1650.0 s	1642.1 s
C=C	1600.0 s	1602.3 s	1599.7 s	1596.8 s	1602.6 s	1602.6 s	1600.0 s	1597.0 m	1599.7 s
(Ar in-plane str)	1560.0 m	1544.7 s	1546.6 s	1536.0 s	1559.2 s	1557.2 s	1525.0 s	1524.0 s	1547.6 s
	1502.0 s	1498.4 s	1490.7 m	1490.7 s	1498.4 s	1499.4 s	-	-	1489.7 s
	1460.0 s	1441.5 s	1443.5 s	1437.7 s	1443.5 s	1448.3 s	1460.0 s	1437.0 s	1443.5 s
C-N (str)	1325.0 s	1307.5 s	1310.4 m	1317.1 s	1344.1 s	1346.0 s	1375.0 s	1321.0 m	1330.6 s
	-	-	-	-	1292.1 s	-	1315.0 m	-	-
C-H (Ar in-plane bend)	1082.0 s	1073.2 m	1099.2 w	1169.6 s	1194.7 m	1179.3 m	1075.0 m	-	1124.3 m
	1042.0 s	1019.2 m	1027.9 w	1027.9 m	1030.8 w	1029.8 w	1030.0 w	-	1031.7 m
C-H (Ar out-of-plane bend)	758.0 s	752.1 s	757.9 s	755.0 s	750.2 s	758.9 s	820.0 s	747.0 s	760.8 s
	723.0 s	691.4 s	695.2 m	698.1 s	690.4 s	729.9 s	742.0 s	715.0 m	727.0 s
C=C (Ar out-of-plane bend)	415.0 m	438.7 m	420.4 w	459.0 w	502.4 s	506.2 s	436.0 s	-	506.2 s

s = strong, m = medium and w = weak, ^aRef. 2.

Table 2. Infrared absorption frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration, 2- $\text{ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHCOR}$, where R =

Assignment	H	CH_3^a	CH_2CH_3	$\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$	$\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$	CH_2Cl^a	CHCl_2^a	CCl_3^a	C_6H_5	2- ClC_6H_4
N-H (str)	3250.4 s	3241.8 s	3288.0 s	3242.7 s	3369.1 s	3266.8 s	3254.3 s	3299.6 s	3224.4 s	3264.9 s
C-H	3114.5 s	3110.6 w	-	3110.6 w	-	-	3125.1 w	3083.6 w	3101.0 w	3102.8 w
(Ar sym str)	3043.1 s	3045.1 w	3033.5 w	3038.3 w	3065.3 w	3044.1 w	3053.7 w	3033.5 w	3059.5 w	3033.5 w
C-H	-	-	2978.5 m	2967.0 s	2965.0 s	2999.7 w	-	-	-	-
(alk str)	2900.4 s	-	2940.9 w	2929.3 w	2929.3 w	2950.6 w	2925.5 w	-	-	-
	2781.8 m	-	-	2874.4 w	2870.5 s	-	-	-	-	-
Combination bands	1940.0 w	1942.9 w	-	-	1955.5 w	1955.5 w	1958.4 w	1952.6 w	1942.3 w	-
	1906.3 w	-	-	-	1924.6 w	1918.8 w	1917.9 w	1923.7 w	1908.2 w	-
	1828.2 w	1912.1 w	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1823.4 w
C=O (str)	1667.2 s	1664.3 s	1664.3 s	1654.6 s	1665.2 s	1673.9 s	1679.7 s	1709.6 s	1652.7 s	1660.4 s
C=C (Ar in-plane str)	1585.2 s	1588.1 s	1584.2 m	1586.2 s	1580.4 s	1587.1 s	1592.9 s	1589.1 s	1579.4 m	1591.0 s
	1542.8 s	1532.2 s	1529.3 s	1533.1 s	1517.7 s	1534.1 s	1542.8 s	1521.6 s	1519.6 s	1525.4 s
	-	1474.3 s	1440.6 s	1475.3 m	1472.4 s	1472.4 m	1475.3 m	1473.4 m	1477.2 s	1480.1 s
	1441.5 s	1438.6 s	1420.3 m	1441.5 s	1438.6 s	1443.5 s	1445.4 s	1443.5 s	1432.9 s	1441.5 s
C-N (str)	1398.1 s	1302.7 s	1367.3 w	1384.6 m	1368.3 s	1328.7 m	1340.3 m	-	1306.5 s	1310.4 s
	1299.8 s	-	1290.1 s	1289.2 s	1293.0 s	1283.4 s	1279.5 m	1292.1 s	-	-
C-H (Ar in-plane bend)	1163.8 s	1060.7 s	1073.2 m	1097.3 s	1057.8 s	1191.8 s	1182.2 w	-	1121.4 m	1131.1 m
	1036.6 s	1011.5 w	1033.7 m	1035.6 s	1033.7 s	1032.7 m	1035.6 s	1035.6 s	1029.8 m	1134.6 m
C-X (str)	1051.0 s	1034.6 s	1056.8 m	1057.8 s	1167.7 s	1056.8 s	1058.7 m	1057.8 s	1058.7 m	1061.6 s
C-H (Ar out-of-plane bend)	790.7 s	755.0 s	755.0 s	752.1 s	753.1 s	757.9 s	807.1 s	823.5 s	750.2 s	747.3 s
	739.6 s	726.1 s	691.4 m	690.4 s	710.6 m	685.6 m	758.9 s	749.2 s	718.4 s	731.9 m

C=C (Ar out-of-plane bend)	441.6 s	449.3 m	448.4 m	450.3 m	448.4 m	447.4 m	446.4 m	452.2 m	446.4 w	461.9 m
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s = strong, m = medium and w = weak, ^aRef. 2.

Table 3. Infrared absorption frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration, 2- $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHCOR}$, where R =

Assignment	CH_3^a	CH_2CH_3	$\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$	$\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$	CH_2Cl^a	CHCl_2^a	CCl_3^a
N-H (str)	3222.5 s	3280.3 s	3269.7 s	3346.9 s	3340.0 s	3254.3 s	3300.0 s
C-H (Ar sym str)	3032.5 w	3033.5 w	3024.8 w	3067.2 w	-	3061.4 w	-
C-H (alk str)	2926.5 w	2973.7 m	2968.9 s	2965.0 m	-	3006.5 w	-
	-	-	2927.4 w	2928.4 w	-	2923.6 w	2930.0 m
	-	-	2872.5 m	2870.5 w	-	-	-
C=O (str)	1652.7 s	1653.7 s	1653.7 s	1655.6 s	1637.0 s	1672.0 s	1705.0 s
C=C (Ar in-plane str)	-	1588.1 m	1587.1 s	1584.2 m	1586.0 s	1590.0 w	1585.0 m
	1540.9 s	1530.2 s	1532.2 s	1519.6 s	-	1551.5 m	1520.0 s
	1490.7 s	1458.9 m	1486.9 w	1485.9 w	1496.0 s	1459.9 w	1480.0 m
	1438.6 m	1423.2 w	1457.9 s	1457.0 m	1441.0 s	-	1460.0 s
C-N (str)	1300.8 s	1371.1 m	1380.8 m	1365.4 m	1318.0 s	1342.2 w	-
	-	1286.3 m	1286.3 m	1296.9 m	1282.0 s	1286.3 w	1290.0 m
C-H (Ar in-plane bend)	-	1074.2 w	1101.2 m	1113.7 w	1055.0 m	1113.7 w	1115.0 m
	1038.5 m	1040.4 w	1037.5 w	1041.4 w	1035.0 m	1035.6 w	1040.0 m
C-H (Ar out-of-plane bend)	751.1 s	753.1 s	749.2 s	756.0 s	760.0 m	759.8 s	765.0 s
	713.5 w	715.5 w	701.0 m	713.5 w	723.0 m	717.4 w	725.0 s
C=C (Ar out-of-plane bend)	454.2 m	446.4 m	445.5 m	447.4 m	446.0 m	446.4 w	448.0 s

s = strong, m = medium and w = weak, ^aRef. 2.**Table 4.** Infrared absorption frequencies (cm^{-1}) of amides of configuration, 2- $\text{ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHCOR}$, where R =

Assignment	CH_3	CH_2CH_3	$\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$	$\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_3$	CH_2Cl^a	CHCl_2^a	CCl_3^a
N-H (str)	3263.3 s	3300.0 s	3296.1 s	3300.0 s	3270.0 s	3278.0 w	3262.0 s
C-H (Ar sym str)	-	3068.5 w	3039.6 w	-	3120.0 m	3093.0 m	-
C-H (alk str)	-	2976.0 w	2974.0 w	2927.7 w	-	2954.0 w	-
	-	2333.7 w	2331.8 m	2864.1 w	-	2992.0 w	-
Combination bands	1901.7 w	-	-	-	-	-	1709.0 w
C=O (str)	1674.1 w	1666.4 s	1662.5 s	1658.7 s	1670.0 s	1681.0 s	1610.0 s
C=C (Ar in-plane str)	1600.8 s	1604.7 m	1593.1 w	1595.0 m	1460.0 s	1550.0 s	1544.0 s
	1487.0 w	1541.0 s	1523.7 m	1529.4 s	-	-	1499.0 s
	-	1488.9 s	-	1487.0 m	-	-	1408.0 s
C-N (str)	1375.2 w	1375.2 m	1294.1 w	1311.5 w	1375.0 s	1288.0 m	1315.0 s
	1313.4 w	1298.0 m	-	1242.1 w	1345.0 m	-	1255.0 s
	1253.6 w	1247.9 m	-	-	1280.0 m	-	1216.0 s
C-H (Ar in-plane bend)	1168.8 w	1082.0 m	1093.6 w	1089.7 w	1180.0 m	-	1099.0 s
	1087.8 m	-	-	1170.7 w	1100.0 m	-	1080.0 m
C-X (str)	1010.6 m	1012.6 w	-	1016.4 w	-	-	1018.0 m

Note

Table-4 (contd.)

C-H (Ar out-of-plane bend)	748.3 w	823.5 s	823.5 m	825.5 m	-	863.0 m	765.0 w
	702.0 w	692.4 m	682.8 w	702.0 w	-	-	661.0 m
C=C (Ar out-of-plane bend)	443.6 s	499.5 m	509.2 w	416.6 w	-	-	435.0 s

s = strong, m = medium and w = weak, ^aRef. 2.

Table 5. Infrared absorption frequencies (cm⁻¹) of amides of configuration, 4-CH₃C₆H₄NHCOR, where R =

Assignment	CH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₃	CH(CH ₃) ₂	C(CH ₃) ₃	CH ₂ Cl ^a	CHCl ₂ ^a	CCl ₃ ^a
N-H (str)	3290.3 s	3267.2 s	3273.0 s	3305.8 s	3365.0 s	3211.0 w	3300.0 s
C-H	3107.1 w	3134.1 w	3041.5 w	-	-	3039.0 w	-
(Ar sym str)	-	-	-	-	-	3025.0 w	-
C-H	2912.3 w	2923.9 w	2972.1 w	2925.8 w	-	2941.0 w	-
(alk str)	2358.8 w	-	2925.8 w	2868.0 w	-	2920.0 w	-
	-	-	2868.0 w	-	-	-	-
Combination bands	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
C=O (str)	1660.6 w	1610.5 s	1658.7 s	1652.9 s	1732.0 s	1674.0 s	1695.0 s
C=C	1604.7 s	1546.8 s	1600.8 w	1600.8 w	1448.0 s	1556.0 m	1600.0 s
(Ar in-plane str)	1508.2 w	1517.9 w	1537.2 m	1523.7 s	-	1516.0 m	1540.0 m
	1446.5 w	1452.3 w	1458.1 w	1473.5 w	-	-	1515.0 m
	-	1409.9 w	1406.0 w	1400.2 w	-	-	1405.0 m
C-N (str)	1317.3 s	1375.2 w	1296.1 w	1315.4 w	1385.0 m	1289.0 m	1248.0 m
	1259.4 w	1303.8 w	1251.7 w	1242.1 w	1330.0 s	-	-
	-	1253.6 w	-	-	1289.0 s	-	-
C-H	-	1201.6 w	1201.6 w	1168.8 w	1154.0 m	-	-
(Ar in-plane bend)	-	1020.3 w	1101.3 w	1026.1 w	-	-	-
	-	-	1024.1 w	-	-	-	-
C-H	754.1 s	813.9 w	813.9 w	810.0 m	888.0 m	871.0 s	790.0 m
(Ar out-of-plane bend)	505.3 s	505.3 w	709.8 w	707.8 w	-	843.0 m	715.0 m
	-	-	-	-	-	808.0 m	-
C=C	462.9 w	443.6 w	418.5 w	416.6 w	-	-	505.0 s

s = strong, m = medium and w = weak, ^aRef. 2.

(phenyl)-, *N*-(2-chlorophenyl)-, *N*-(2-methylphenyl)-, *N*-(4-chlorophenyl)- and *N*-(4-methylphenyl)-amides, respectively. Generally variations in the C=O stretching vibrations did not show particular trends on chloro or methyl group substitution in the side chain. The N-H stretching vibrations also appear as strong vibrations in the ranges, 3337–3240, 3369–3242, 3347–3223, 3300–3262 and 3365–3211 cm⁻¹ for the *N*-(phenyl)-, *N*-(2-chlorophenyl)-, *N*-(2-methylphenyl)-, *N*-(4-chlorophenyl)- and *N*-(4-methylphenyl)-amides, respectively. The effect of side chain substitution on the N-H absorptions did not show particular trends. Similarly the C-N stretching vibrations also did not

show regular trends with substitution in the side chain. This may be due to the fact that the spectra of the compounds are recorded in the solid state and the compounds may crystallise in different forms in the solid state.

The other frequencies are assigned to various other vibrations of the ring (Tables 1–5). The discussions are similar to the other organic aromatic compounds in general. The same is not reported here. The intercorelation of C=O and N-H absorption frequencies of *N*-(phenyl)-, *N*-(2-chlorophenyl)-, *N*-(2-methylphenyl)-, *N*-(4-chlorophenyl)- and *N*-(4-methylphenyl)-amides were reasonably linear with some exceptions as some of the compounds may crystallise

in entirely different forms.

Experimental

The mono- and di-substituted phenylamides were prepared from substituted anilines, substituted acetic acids and thionyl chloride. The infrared spectra were recorded on a JASCO-430 (Japan) FT/IR spectrometer. The resolution was set to 4 cm^{-1} and the scanning range was $400\text{--}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The spectra were measured in the solid state as pressed KBr pellets (13 mm).

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